

Book Review

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Understanding International Students from Asia in American Universities: Learning and Living Globalization

Edited by Yingyi Ma and Martha A. Garcia-Murillo, Springer ISBN-13: 978-3319603926

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In this book, the editors suggest that the intensity of globalization is helping to reshape the American Education System. The reshaping of the American educational system is reflected in the number of students the United States accommodates from different parts of the world. With an international student count of 1.09 million; the United States is one of the primary destinations for international students in the world. Interestingly, Chinese, Indian, and South Korean students represent more than half (51%) of the overall number of international students in the United States. However, Asian students combined represent 64.3% of the overall number of international students in America, making them the dominant group of students (Ma & Garcia-Murillo, 2018, p. 1). The book provides important insight on the issue of international student experiences which can be applied as a guide for administrators, faculty, staff and domestic students who are interested in cultivating the ideal environment, where these students not only add to the diversity of the student population, but also enhance the exchange of ideas, and expand or increase cultural understanding in and out of the classroom

This work is organized as a collection of research articles drawn from experts in the fields of “sociology, higher education, and communication and rhetoric studies” (p. 8); *Understanding International Students from Asia in American Universities* is divided into three major parts and has a total of 12 chapters covering Asian international students’ experiences over their life span. Part I provides insight on the experiences of this group prior to traveling to the United States. Part II includes the academic aspect of Asian international students and their perceptions during their enrolment at U.S. universities. Moreover, this section captures topics such as intercultural attitudinal changes, prejudice and discrimination based on religion, stereotypes and verbal discrimination, and academic barriers. Part III focuses on factors that influence the Asian international students’ decisions to stay in the U.S.

This book is a call for administrators, faculty, and policy makers to take proactive steps to enhance Asian international students experience in American universities. To arrive at their conclusion, the authors employ diverse methodologies, “ranging from survey data to in depth

interviews to mixed methods” (p. 8). This edited volume of the book provides an opportunity for further research on international students.

Chapter one by Yingyi Ma presents the issue of “Paradigm shift: Learning Is a “Two-way Street” which suggests that Asian students are expected to learn, adapt and adjust to the American culture upon their arrival into the country. Conversely, there is no requirement on the part of American learners in terms of adaptation to the culture of foreign students. In this chapter, Ma and Garcia-Murillo argue that learning should be reciprocal where each party involved learn from one another. Kim, Bankart, Jiang, and Brazil write chapter two of the book which is based on those factors that motivate Asian international students to study abroad. Kim, Bankart, Jiang, and Brazil’s findings indicate that the primary reason that Asian international students pursue their studies abroad is due to the employment opportunities of the chosen country. In Chapter three, Adrienne Lee Atterberry focuses on women from India pursuing their MBA degree in the United State. Adrienne Lee Atterberry states that for the most part, these students chose the United States as their study destination because of financial aid availability, the network of support (i.e. such as family and friends), and general exposure to the experience of attending an American institution. In Chapter four, C. N. Le discusses students in China and their concerns, expectations and motivation to pursue higher education in the United States. In the chapter the author discusses how Chinese students prepared themselves for the financial rigors of studying abroad by familiarizing themselves with the resources that are available to them. Elisabeth Gareis and Ardalan Jalayer chapter five on “intercultural friendship between East Asian students and American domestic students” reports that intercultural contact eliminates stereotypes and prejudices among foreigners and domestic students. Chapter six by Maheen Haider focuses on issues of discrimination that Asian international student’s experience. Maheen Haider examine the cases of Muslim-Pakistani international students in the United States. The findings suggest that Pakistani students felt compelled to constantly defend themselves against the discriminatory acts perpetrated against them in the host country. Moreover, this defensive approach evolved into a coping strategy coined “the double consciousness” which is used to deal with the negativity of discrimination. Eunyoung Kim chapter seven highlights the acculturation issues of Korean students and their attempts at adjustment to the campus environment. Chapter eight by Vivian Louie is a discourse on “power asymmetries in American universities” (p. 149). In this chapter Louie examines Chinese MBA students’ experience. According to the findings of the author, Chinese students come to the United States expecting to be treated fairly and equally. However, upon their arrival Chinese students are not only faced with academic, language and cultural barriers; but they also are faced with the realization that deference is not always given to the skills/knowledge that they bring to the host country. Chapter 9 of Xiaqiong You and Xiaoye You illustrate the altruism of American professors in terms of exceeding expectations and going the extra-mile to support Chinese students in their reading and writing courses. Moreover, the authors recommend that these examples of altruism serve as a model for other professors at American universities. Peter Briggs in chapter 10 outline the growth of Chinese undergraduates at Michigan State University and how the university responded to the growth of this population group. In this chapter, Briggs discusses how the population of Chinese international undergraduate students ‘grew exponentially; and how that growth triggered changes in terms of the university preparedness to accommodate the high number of Chinese students on their campus. Chapters 11 and 12 debate the challenges that Asian international students face after completing their studies in United States. In chapter 11, Dongbin Kim, Jin-young Roh, and Taylor de Barroso provide an analysis of the factors that influence Asian international doctoral students’ decision to remain in America after completing their programs at American universities. Chapter 12 by Martha A.

Garcia-Murillo addresses Asian international alumni and the leadership skills acquired during their education in American universities and how these skills assisted them in their personal and professional development. The authors recommend that universities consider implementing more leadership programs to facilitate productive international student experience.

This book offers an insightful discussion into the lives of international students from Asia. For academic instructors this book can be integrated into the classroom curriculum to generate discussions on the challenges facing international students. Additionally, the book could serve as a guide to policy makers in the creation of benchmarks that facilitate progressive learning environments for foreigners and nationals. The book is a reliable source that can be utilized as a training tool for the effective development of leadership skills in international students.
